

Newsletter 10 / 2021

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Save the date

Please register for the free **ESA-ECMWF WORKSHOP on Machine Learning for Earth System Observation and Prediction**, 15-18 November 2021, ESA-ESRIN, Hybrid Event, Free to attend, registrations are open

<https://www.ml4esop.esa.int/>

Spread the word

New call in ESIWACE2 Service 1 for 2022 is now open!

We are looking forward to a new phase of supporting weather and climate modeling groups in their efforts to prepare for new hardware platforms and the upcoming generation of (pre-)Exascale supercomputers. Service 1, in which the new call is open, targets model developing groups and assists with porting the codes to new hardware platforms such as GPUs. For more information on the call and on how to apply, please visit the [ESiWACE services web page on Refactoring and Porting](#). **This ESIWACE2 Service 1 call is open for applications until November 1, 2021.**

Events that ESIWACE will participate in or has participated in

- [SC21](#), St. Louis, MO, USA, 14-19 November, 2021
- [Training on HPDA for climate data with the Ophidia framework](#), online, 11 November, 2021
- [Advanced C++ workshop](#), online, 11-13 October, 2021
- [19th workshop on HPC in meteorology](#), online, 20-24 September, 2021
- [IEEE eScience](#), online, 20-23 September, 2021
- [Training on High Performance Data Analytics and Visualisation](#), online, 13-16 September, 2021
- [Summer School on effective HPC for weather and climate](#), online, 23-27 August, 2021

News & updates

XIOS and Cylc User Support 2021 successfully allocated

Within its User Service 2 for 2021, ESIWACE2 has in total offered 5 person-months of Dedicated User Support: 3 person-months of Cylc support and 2 person-months of support for XIOS.

The Cylc User Support 2021 has been granted to ICM, the Interdisciplinary Centre for Mathematical and Computational Modelling in Poland, and will comprise assistance in the design and optimisation of the general workflow of the ICM coupled model.

One person-month of support for XIOS has been allocated to both the Met Office and to Mercator Ocean/LOCEAN-IPSL. The Met Office (UK) applied for the development of a specific functionality in XIOS, i.e. the support of parametric vertical coordinates described in the CF standard, in order to consolidate its use of XIOS in their new LFRic atmosphere model. Mercator-Ocean and LOCEAN-IPSL (France) mainly target the implementation and optimisation of the input functionality of XIOS in order to decrease the overhead observed when reading the new ERA5 reanalysis data.

Further information:

<https://www.esiwace.eu/news/news/cylc-user-support-2021-allocated-to-icm-poland>

<https://www.esiwace.eu/news/news/xios-user-support-2021-allocated-to-met-office-and-mercator-ocean-locean-ipsl>

Summer School on Effective HPC for Climate and Weather

The 2021 summer school took place in August and covered the topics of extreme-scale computation, parallel programming in practice, modern storage, middleware and file formats, machine learning, high-performance data analytics and visualisation, performance analysis, and containers. Similarly to our last year's summer school, it was organised fully virtual due to the COVID restrictions. We aimed to exploit the virtual format as much as possible and created videos of the sessions to allow even more attendees to enjoy the training.

Overall, the lecturers evolved their material, delivering 16 hours of lectures and 8 hours of hands-on and lab practicals. The summer school attracted participants from all over the world with significantly varying scientific backgrounds and levels of qualification. Overall, 125 people registered for the summer school, some of them interested in receiving the information about the videos. There were 22 responses from the post-event survey with 95% of the attendees saying they had at least a good experience. The attendance was between 30 - 50 people per session affiliated to institutions in 31 countries. 33 of the attendees received a certificate of attendance because they had attended more than 60% of all sessions. We believe that the lectures and lab practicals were generally well-received and a successful replacement for an in-person summer school.

Summer school event page: <https://www.esiwace.eu/events/summer-school-2021>

ESiWACE2 Training on High Performance Data Analytics and Visualisation

The second training course on High Performance Data Analytics (HPDA) and Visualisation, organised by CMCC and DKRZ in the context of ESiWACE2, consisted of four 2-hour online sessions held from 13 to 16 September 2021.

The course was aimed at increasing participants' expertise on analytics and visualisation applied to climate and weather data through the Ophidia and ParaView open source solutions.

The topics covered by the training included the introduction to scientific data management, analysis and visualisation, interactive analysis, data analytics workflows and an overview of visualisation workflows, from post to in-situ. Besides introductory lectures, the course provided examples of real world applications, walkthrough tutorials and practical hands-on sessions.

More than 60 people from around 20 countries worldwide registered for the 2021 training. Additional information about the event is available at: <https://indico.dkrz.de/e/esiwace-hpda-vis-2021>

19th Workshop on High Performance Computing in Meteorology

ECMWF hosted the 19th Workshop on High Performance Computing in Meteorology from 20 to 24 September, bringing together experts from national weather centres, academia and industry. The theme of this year's online edition was 'Towards Exascale Computing in Numerical Weather Prediction'.

A total of 313 participants from 43 countries took part in the event. They could follow more than 50 talks, including three keynotes from leading experts in high-performance computing (HPC). You can find further information [here](#).

Snapshots

Atos (BULL)

Atos Bull is currently working on HPC user-service projects AGRIF, FESOM2 and RTE+RRTMGP C++ in collaboration with NLeSC. AGRIF has been integrated into the NEMO BENCH configuration and some profiling allowed to identify optimisation options, which are ongoing. On FESOM2, the most important loops have been extracted from the tracer advection function, optimised on GPU with OpenACC and then re-integrated. Final results will come soon.

BSC

BSC has been performing test and scalability runs for the Very High Resolution EC-Earth4 configuration on Mare Nostrum4. The configuration is stable and ready to provide insights into the computational performance. The details will be published in deliverable D1.1 (due in December 2021).

CERFACS

CERFACS has produced Open Educational Resources (OER) material based on the Small Private Online Course (SPOC) on OASIS3-MCT realised within ESIWACE2 (<https://www.oercommons.org/courseware/lesson/85340/overview>).

CERFACS has also organised the calls for XIOS and Cylc 2021 Dedicated User Support. For XIOS, the 2021 support has been allocated to the UK Met Office and Mercator-Ocean/LOCEAN-IPSL proposals. For Cylc, the 2021 support has been allocated to ICM (Poland) for assistance in design and optimisation of the general workflow of the ICM coupled model.

CMCC

CMCC has, jointly with DKRZ, organised the 2021 online training course on High Performance Data Analytics (HPDA) and Visualisation, held from 13 to 16 September.

The development of the Ophidia extensions for in-flight analytics via the ESDM streaming API continued in order to support additional analytical features. Moreover, the ESDM-PAV runtime development is also proceeding to increase the features for the support of ESDM data management within PAV experiments.

DKRZ

Together with MPI-M, we have performed a 2-month 1.25 km resolution (R2B11) ICON ocean simulation, which shows a massive increase in ocean eddy activity. Animated visualisations of this very high resolution dataset, as well as of coupled ICON ocean and atmosphere simulations at 5 km resolution, have been published on the ESiWACE YouTube channel. More work on DYAMOND winter data standardisation and usage of the intake library in python is under way. In collaboration with the NextGEMS project, documentation on how to work with DYAMOND data sets is provided via easy.gems.dkrz.de.

We have also co-organised and held this year's online training course on High Performance Data Analytics (HPDA) and Visualisation together with CMCC.

We have relaunched the ESiWACE project website and are further revising and improving the content of the page. Furthermore we have organised and hosted this year's ESiWACE2 annual project meeting, which took place as a fully virtual event from 27 to 29 September 2021.

ECMWF

We hosted the 19th Workshop on High Performance Computing in Meteorology as a virtual event from 20 to 24 September with many speakers from science and industry, including a couple of ESiWACE partners.

NLeSC

The Netherlands eScience Center has been preparing the call for projects for 2022 for Service 1, which creates collaborative projects related to performance optimisations and readying codes for the pre-exascale systems. The call has recently been released on the ESiWACE website.

In the meantime, the research software engineers at the eScience center are continuing the work in the Service 1 projects running in 2021, including the projects on DALES and RTE+RRTMGP-CPP.

UKRI/STFC

We have continued developing support in PSyclone to translate from our internal representation to the representation used by the Dawn DSL. We have continued to improve support for running NEMO on GPUs using PSyclone. The full code, including sea-ice, now runs faster on a V100 GPU than a Skylake CPU. There are multi-gpu scaling issues when running NEMO, which are under investigation. We are contributing to the concurrent components task by providing a paper study of potential high-level concurrency in the LFRic model. We presented at the upcoming ECMWF HPC workshop and with MeteoSwiss we organised and presented at one of the sessions or the ESiWACE2 summer school.

University of Reading

We have organised and hosted the second virtual Summer School on Effective HPC for Weather and Climate.

Recent ESiWACE2-related Publications

Adewoyin, R.A., Dueben, P., Watson, P. et al. TRU-NET: a deep learning approach to high resolution prediction of rainfall. Mach Learn **110**, 2035–2062 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10994-021-06022-6>

Agarwal, N., Kondrashov, D., Dueben, P., Ryzhov, E., & Berloff, P. A comparison of data-driven approaches to build low-dimensional ocean models. *Journal of Advances in Modeling Earth Systems*, 13, (2021). e2021MS002537, <https://doi.org/10.1029/2021MS002537>

Zeman, C., Wedi, N. P., Dueben, P. D., Ban, N., and Schär, C.: Model intercomparison of COSMO 5.0 and IFS 45r1 at kilometer-scale grid spacing, *Geosci. Model Dev.*, 14, 4617–4639 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-14-4617-2021>

News from the neighbors

IS-ENES3 Virtual clinic on bias-adjustment of climate model data

For many studies on the impacts of climate change, bias-adjustment of the climate model simulations is a necessary step before impact models can be run or before relevant climate indices can be calculated. However, there are many methods, all with their own advantages and disadvantages.

The [IS-ENES3 project](#) organises a virtual clinic to give in-depth information on these methods, divided into two meetings:

- 1st meeting: **14th October 2021**, 10:00-12:00 CET
- 2nd meeting: **21st October 2021**, 10:00-12:00 CET

The workshop is for everyone interested, especially for **climate researchers, impact researchers and climate service providers** who may have to do bias-adjustments or use/will use bias-adjusted climate model data. There is no registration fee. Find all information and the registration form [here](#)! The registration deadline is October 12th.

Start of the project “NextGEMS: Next Generation Earth Modelling Systems”

On **1st September 2021** NextGEMS, a European research project, started. It will develop and apply a new generation of global coupled Storm-Resolving Earth System Models (SR-ESMs) for the study of anthropogenic climate change.

It is funded by the European Commission’s H2020 programme and its consortium consists of 26 institutes from 14 countries. **ESIWACE** will tightly collaborate with nextGEMS in defining scientifically useful configurations of SR-ESMs that shall eventually be run on EuroHPC pre-exascale and exascale systems.

One central part of the project are hackathons enabling the SR-ESM community to work with this new kind of simulation data, to advance model development and to involve a broader community in Earth-system modelling. The **first hackathon will take place from 19th October to 22nd October 2021** at the Harnack House in Berlin, Germany. The participants will analyse the DYAMOND winter simulation runs, which are supported by **ESIWACE**. In addition, the hackathon will technically be supported by DKRZ.

More information about NextGEMS can be found on the project website at: <https://nextgems-h2020.eu/>.

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